

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART IV.

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In view of the fact that glyoxalinoquinolines of Narang and Rây have the requisite antiseptic properties against paramaecia, benziminazolylquinoline derivatives, which are expected to possess antimalarial properties, have been synthesised

Glyoxalinoquinoline, synthesised by Narang and Rây (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 976), has the requisite antiseptic properties as tested against paramaecia in a dilution of 1 : 1000, but the compounds of this series have very feeble basicity and do not give stable salts (*cf.* Rây, Presidential Address, *Proc. Indian Sci. Congress*, 1937, p. 103). In view of this important observation, it seemed of considerable interest to synthesise some benziminazolylquinoline derivatives, which are expected to possess antimalarial properties. The presence of the benziminazole residue is likely to impart pronounced basicity to these products.

In a previous communication (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 89) it has been shown that the condensation of thioacetylcarbamic acid derivatives with diamines constitutes a general method for the synthesis of iminazole derivatives. Following the same method, the benziminazole derivative (I, R=Et) has now been synthesised by reacting acetylcarbethoxythioacetocarbamic acid with *o*-phenylenediamine. Its constitution has been established by its conversion to 2-methylbenziminazole (Hübner, *Annalen*, 1881, 209, 353) by alkali hydrolysis. With concentrated hydrochloric acid it yields the acid (I, R=H). Both these compounds (I, R=H

* In the formulae in this paper X stands for

or Et) react with phenylhydrazine to yield the benziminazolylpyrazolone derivative (II). Because of the presence of both iminazole and pyrazolone rings, the compound (II) is expected to exhibit important therapeutic properties.

The compound (I, R = Et) readily condenses with aniline at 180° to yield the anilide (III). When treated with concentrated sulphuric acid at 100° the compound (III) furnishes the benziminazolylquinoline derivative (IV) (*cf.* Knorr, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 772). It is, however, to be observed that, during the treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid, the resulting product (IV) gets sulphonated.

Acetylacetonanilide, obtained by condensing acetylacetone with aniline, yields 2:4-dimethylquinoline, when treated with sulphuric acid (Combes, *Compt. rend.*, 1887, 106, 142; *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1888, 49, 90). Taking advantage of this reaction, the benzimidazole derivative (V), previously synthesised (Ghosh, *loc. cit.*), has now been condensed with aniline at 145-150° to yield (VI). When treated with concentrated sulphuric acid at 100°, the compound (VI) yields the benziminazolylquinoline derivative (VII).

When, however, condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine at 150°, the compound (V) yields (VIII) with elimination of two molecules of water (*cf.* Thiele and Steimmig, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 955).

(VIII)

As regards the basicity of the two benziminazolyl quinoline derivatives, (IV) and (VII), the former forms a stable hydrochloride, which is very soluble in cold water and is, thus, suitable for pharmacological examination. The latter also yields a hydrochloride which is very soluble in cold water, but the aqueous solution slowly precipitates the base.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Carboethoxyacetylmethylbenziminazole (I, R=Et).—To an alcoholic solution of acetylcarbethoxythioacetocarbamic acid (23.3 g.; prepared according to the method of Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Inst. Sci.*, 1933, **16A**, 107), *o*-phenylenediamine (10.8 g.) was slowly added, when the reaction at once began with evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen and rise in temperature. The solution was heated under reflux for about 2 hours, cooled and diluted with water, when a semi-solid mass was obtained. It was purified by dissolving in dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitating with excess of sodium bicarbonate solution. The solid, thus obtained, was crystallised from hot water in colourless needles, m. p. 128-29°, yield 14 g. (Found: N, 11.12. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 11.38 per cent). It is insoluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution, but readily soluble in cold dilute hydrochloric acid and also in dilute alkali.

A solution of the above compound in excess of alcoholic potash (15%) was heated under reflux for about 3 hours and the solution was evaporated nearly to dryness on a water-bath. The aqueous solution of the mass was acidified with acetic acid and filtered. The acid solution was treated with excess of sodium bicarbonate; the solution, on standing, gave a precipitate

tate which crystallised from water in colourless needles, m. p. 170° (mixed m. p. with 2-methylbenzimidazole, Hübner, *loc. cit.*). (Found; N, 21'37. $C_8H_8N_2$ requires N, 21'21 per cent).

2-Carboxyacetylmethylbenzimidazole (I, R=H).—A solution of the above compound in concentrated hydrochloric acid was boiled for 30 minutes, diluted with water and the solution evaporated to a small bulk. On cooling, a crystalline solid (hydrochloride) was obtained, which crystallised from water, acidulated with few drops of hydrochloric acid, in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. $290-91^{\circ}$. An aqueous solution of this hydrochloride was treated with excess of sodium acetate, when a solid was precipitated, which crystallised from water in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 172° . (Found : N, 12'61. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3N_2$ requires N, 12'84 per cent). It is readily soluble in aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution.

1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2')-benzimidazolylpyrazolone (II).—A glacial acetic acid solution of the compound (I, R=Et; 2'5 g.) and phenylhydrazine (1'1 g.) was heated under reflux for about 2 hours. The solution was diluted with water and evaporated to a small bulk. When treated with excess of sodium bicarbonate solution, a solid was obtained which was purified by dissolving in cold dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitating with sodium bicarbonate solution. It crystallised from hot water in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. $172-73^{\circ}$, yield 1 g. (Found : N, 19'28. $C_{17}H_{14}ON_4$ requires N, 19'31 per cent). It is readily soluble in cold dilute alkali. A solution of the compound in cold dilute hydrochloric acid was evaporated to a small bulk, when, on cooling, the hydrochloride was obtained, which crystallised from a small quantity of water in almost colourless rectangular plates, m. p. $282-84^{\circ}$. It is readily soluble in cold water.

The same compound (m. p. $172-73^{\circ}$) was obtained, when the compound (I, R=H) was allowed to react with phenylhydrazine under similar conditions. Identity was confirmed by mixed m.p. and other properties.

Condensation of the Compound (I, R=Et) with Aniline : Formation of the Anilide (III).—A mixture of the compound (I, R=Et; 7'4 g.) and aniline (2'8 g.) was heated at 170° for about 1 hour. The solid obtained was cooled, triturated with cold alcohol and filtered. It crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in colourless shining plates, m. p. 255° (decomp., producing a bright red colouration), yield 5'5 g. (Found : N, 14'21. $C_{17}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 14'33 per cent). It is insoluble in cold dilute alkali.

2-Hydroxy-3-(2')-benzimidazolyl-4-methylquinoline-sulphonic Acid (IV).—A solution of the above compound (III; 5 g.) in concen-

trated sulphuric acid (33 c. c.) was heated on an oil-bath at 100° for 1½ hours. When cooled, the reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water, when a brown solid (4 g.) was obtained. It was filtered and washed several times with alcohol. It was purified by dissolving in aqueous bicarbonate solution and precipitating with dilute hydrochloric acid. It is insoluble in hot alcohol or glacial acetic acid. It is sparingly soluble in boiling water, from which it was crystallised (charcoal) in colourless plates, m. p. 293-95° (decomp.). [Found: N, 11.72; S, 8.53; M. W. (by titration), 358. $C_{17}H_{11}O_1N_1S$ requires N, 11.83; S, 9.01 per cent. M. W., 355].

The clear solution, obtained by heating the above compound with concentrated hydrochloric acid, was diluted with water and evaporated to a small bulk, when the hydrochloride was obtained. It crystallised from water in colourless needles, which turned grey above 240° and did not melt even at 310°. [Found (in a sample dried at 120°): N, 10.48. $C_{17}H_{13}O_4N_3S$, HCl requires N, 10.74 per cent). It is readily soluble in cold water and remains stable in solution. The aqueous solution, when treated with excess of sodium acetate, precipitates the above compound (IV mixed m. p. 293-95°).

δ-Phenylimido-γ-(2'-benziminazolyl-β-ketopentane (VI).—A mixture of aniline (9.3 g.) and 2-diacetylmethylbenziminazole (21.6 g., prepared according to the method of Ghosh, *loc. cit.*) was heated on an oil-bath at 145°-50° for 2 hours, when there was elimination of water vapour. The cold molten mass was triturated with benzene, when a solid was obtained which was filtered and washed with benzene. It is practically insoluble in alcohol and crystallises from glacial acetic acid in colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 315-16° (decomp., producing a red colouration), yield 8 g. (Found: N, 14.21. $C_{18}H_{17}ON_3$ requires N, 14.43 per cent). It is insoluble in dilute hydrochloric acid but readily soluble in cold concentrated acid.

2:4-Dimethyl-3-(2'-benziminazolyl)quinoline (VII).—A solution of the above compound (VI, 6 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (35 c.c.) was heated on an oil-bath at 100° for 30 minutes, cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The clear acid solution was treated with excess of sodium bicarbonate, when a solid was precipitated. It is readily soluble in acetic acid and crystallises from a large quantity of alcohol in colourless needles, m.p. 328-30° (producing a red colouration), yield 3 g. (Found: N, 15.11. $C_{18}H_{15}N_3$ requires N, 15.38 per cent). The *picrate* was obtained as yellow needles, m.p. 250° (decomp., producing a deep red colouration).

The above compound (VII) was dissolved in cold dilute hydrochloric acid; the acid solution on evaporation to a small bulk yielded the hydrochloride as colourless rectangular plates, m. p. above 300°. It is readily soluble in cold water; the aqueous solution on standing precipitates the base (mixed m. p. 328-30°).

2:4-Dimethyl-3-(2')-benziminazolyl-6:7-benzo-1:5-heptadiazine (VIII) — An intimate mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine (3.6 g.) and 2-diacetylmethylbenziminazole (7.2 g.) was heated at 150° for 2 hours. The temperature was raised to 180° for about 10 minutes and the mass allowed to cool. It was triturated with benzene, when a solid was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in yellowish rectangular plates, m. p. above 310°, yield 3 g. (Found: N, 19.42. $C_{18}H_{16}N_4$ requires N, 19.44 per cent). It does not contain any diazotisable amino group. It is readily soluble in cold dilute hydrochloric acid; the acid solution, on evaporation to a small bulk, yielded the hydrochloride in the form of colourless rectangular plates, m. p. above 300°. This hydrochloride is readily soluble in cold water.

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